

THE ROLE OF COMPOUND WORDS IN THE WORD-FORMATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the comparative study of the formation, functioning, and semantics of the so-called compound words in Modern English and Uzbek. The author paid special attention to the nature of compound nouns and verbs, the way they are joined as well as the way they denote definite notions. In his investigation, the author relies on the opinion of the leading specialists in English and Uzbek linguistics and applies them critically. The article may be of interest to learners of English and Uzbek morphology and lexicology.*

Keywords: *compound words, compound nouns, compound verbs, the root, joint words, etc.*

It is known that each language's vocabulary constantly improves. Some of the extralinguistic and linguistic processes can be the reason for improving and expanding linguistic vocabulary. New words, phrases, and phraseological combinations that emerge from the internal evolution of the language are examples of linguistic elements that improve the vocabulary of the language. extralinguistic and linguistic aspects that influence the growth of the language's vocabulary are social, political, cultural, and economic developments. These phenomena include the impact of the conqueror language on the conquered language as a result of one nation being conquered by another (e.g., alterations in the English language's composition due to the French language's supremacy in this).

Extralinguistic events that affect the growth of the vocabulary of the language include social, political, cultural, and economic events that can affect the language. Such phenomena include the influence of the language of the conquerors on the language of the conquered due to the conquest of one country by another country (for example, changes in the structure of the English language as a result of the dominance of the French language in this country for a certain period due to the conquest of England by the Normans in 1066, or the former Soviet power changes in the structure of the languages of the national republics based on the pressure exerted by the Russian language on the national languages of the allied republics during the rule), or Arabic words that entered the Uzbek language as a result of the Arab invasion and the introduction of Islam) as a result of the regular development of economic and cultural relations between the countries, the words of the same language became the second entering the language (economic terms, concepts (for example: *bankruptcy, creditor*) and words that have found their place in the new consumption after being re-used (*potential, ministry, investment, owner*) due to socio-political changes taking place in the country (for example, political and legal terms (*sezd, oblast, rayon, sudlov, court, prosecutor, lawyer*) and concepts) new words that appear, etc.

Among the linguistic factors of the development of the language vocabulary are new words that appear directly based on the internal laws of the language, and language units that appear through the creation and use of terms. Such units naturally arise through the word formation system. Word formation emerged as a connecting tool between the components of the language called lexicology and grammar (morphology), which studies the nature of newly emerging words

in the language, the methods of their formation, the norms of their spread in the language (whether a certain method is productive or less productive). Studying the laws of word formation and its system opens the way to determining the rich internal possibilities of the language and the perspectives of word formation and studying the laws of orthography. The following methods are available in the current word formation: morphological method, morphological-syntactic method, lexical-syntactic, and lexical-semantic methods are known.

We can witness that these methods are widely used in the languages being compared. Among them, one of the most common methods is the morphological method. In this case, the root part of words (Greek morphos-shape) is the main building material. Additions (affixes) with a new meaning are attached to this stem. There are several factors of word formation in the languages being compared, and it seems appropriate to give a brief description of each of them and strengthen the ideas expressed with practical examples. Such factors can include the methods of word formation called affixation, word composition, conversion, and abbreviation or shortening.

Another common word formation method in comparative languages is *the conversion* method, in which a one-word group is formed from the core of another word group. Since morphological indicators in English have not developed widely in the Uzbek language, word formation in English through the conversion method is a common method. For example:

work - to work, paper - to paper, walk- to walk, song – to sing paper – to paper, love - to love, wireless - to wireless.

Due to the abundance of suffixes that can be added to the root of a word in the Uzbek language, a suffix is added to it even when a word is formed by the conversion method, unlike in English. For example:

arra - arra-la-moq, qo‘zi - qo‘zila-moq, ko‘z – ko‘z-la-moq, zo‘r – zo‘r-la-moq, etc.

Word composition, which is one of the productive methods of word formation, is one of the methods characteristic of both languages under comparison. In this case, words with new meanings are formed by joining two stems or bases to one stem or base. For example:

English in the language: week-end, office management, postage-stamp, aircraft carrier, shoe-maker, bottle-opener, school-master, horseracing, post office, headache, horseshoe, earthquake, screwdriver, sunset, etc.

Uzbek in the language: boshpana, Oltiariq, gultojixo‘roz , beshpanja , gulqaychi, oshqovoq, to‘yxona etc.

Conclusion

In conclusion, from what has been analyzed above it can be inferred as follows that behind the load names mentioned above, the methods of joint word formation, as we said, their productivity with, every both to the language special has been common and some received language for special has been private aspects with, of own I structural in the structure components with and finally, they expressed semantic of meanings to himself dependence of h with behind the wheel to the language received word to make methods separately separate stands _ Therefore we preferred to analyze the subject into the seasons.

REFERENCES

1. В.Д.Аракин Лингвистическая типология и методика обучения иностранным языкам. “Вопросы теории методики преподавания иностранных языков”. Казань, 1969, 77.

2. Абдурахмонов Ғ., А. Сайфуллаев, Ҳ. Рустамов. Она тили. Т., 1995.
3. Абдурахмонов Ғ., Ш.Шукуров. Ўзбек тилининг тарихий грамматикаси. Т., 1973.
4. Абдурахмонов Ҳ., А. Рафиев. Ўзбек тилининг амалий грамматикаси. Т., 1992.
5. Амосова Н.Н. Основы английской фразеологии. ЛГУ, 1963
6. Арнолд И.В. Стилистика современного английского языка Л.1981.
7. Арнольд И.В. Лексикология современног английского языка. (The English Word) М., 1973.
8. Арутюнова Н.Д. Очерки по словообразованию в современном испанском языке. М.,1961.
9. Ахманова О.С. К вопросу об отличие сложных слов от фразеологических единиц. Труды ИЯ., т.1У, М., 1954
10. Бархударов Л.С. Русско-английские языкоые параллели. РЯЗР, 1972.
11. Баскаков Б.А. Содиқов А.С. Абдуазизов А.А. Умумий тилшунослик, Т., 1989 й.